

Large Language Models in Secondary Informatics Education: Teachers' Perspectives

Leonard Busuttill¹[0000-0003-3779-891X]

Faculty of Education, University of Malta, Malta
leonard.busuttill@um.edu.mt

Abstract. This study explores secondary Informatics teachers' perspectives on integrating large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT into their teaching practices. Twenty-one teachers teaching informatics in secondary schools participated in workshops where they engaged with LLMs and discussed their classroom applications. Teachers identified benefits such as enhanced student engagement, personalised support, facilitation of complex explorations, and real-world preparation. However, challenges emerged, such as revising assessment methods and fostering students' critical evaluation of AI outputs. Teachers also expressed concerns about potential overreliance on technology. Practical issues like data privacy, access limitations, and the necessity for structured training programs were also highlighted. While teachers see LLMs as valuable tools for enriching Informatics education, effective integration requires addressing assessment challenges, ensuring critical evaluation skills, and providing robust training and infrastructure. To fully realise the potential of LLMs in Informatics education, stakeholders must prioritise assessment reform, embed critical thinking instruction, and invest in comprehensive teacher training and infrastructure.

Keywords: Large Language Models (LLMs) · Informatics Education · Teacher Perspectives · AI Integration in Classrooms.

1 Introduction

The emergence of ChatGPT and similar generative AI (GenAI) tools has significantly influenced education. These tools support personalised learning by adapting content to individual needs, enhancing inclusivity, engagement, and classroom management [1, 21].

Educators also benefit from GenAI through automation of routine tasks such as grading and feedback, which allows more time for pedagogy and student interaction [5, 30]. GenAI additionally supports curriculum design by generating materials and assessments, enriching the learning experience [20]. Beyond automation, hybrid intelligence systems—where educators and AI collaborate—are enabling innovative pedagogical strategies that combine human creativity with AI's analytical strengths [6].

GenAI has been found to foster self-regulated learning behaviours such as goal-setting and help-seeking, especially in science education [22], and to promote dynamic, accessible learning environments [10]. These systems can adapt to students' evolving needs and support more reflective learning experiences [6].

Nonetheless, challenges persist. Concerns include data privacy, infrastructure demands, and ethical risks, such as plagiarism and bias in AI-generated content [16, 15, 17, 28]. Critics also warn that GenAI may encourage superficial learning and hinder the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills [17].

As AI increasingly handles administrative and cognitive tasks, the educator's role is shifting toward supporting learning processes beyond content delivery [2]. Frameworks like technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) have been proposed to guide effective integration of AI into subject teaching [18]. In parallel, calls have emerged to embed AI literacy into the curriculum to develop students' higher-order thinking skills in AI-enhanced environments [5, 12].

Informatics education raises specific considerations in the integration of GenAI. Tools such as GitHub Copilot and ChatGPT are increasingly used in the teaching of programming, assisting learners by generating code and offering immediate feedback. Their effectiveness, however, depends on students' ability to critically evaluate AI-generated content [19, 23, 24].

GenAI has been shown to improve the code authoring of novice programmers without affecting their ability to edit or understand code [13]. Yet, concerns persist around over-reliance and the erosion of foundational skills. A balanced integration—combining GenAI with problem-solving exercises—is crucial for fostering deep understanding [29, 8, 27].

Academic integrity also presents a challenge. Educators have raised concerns about plagiarism and the need to reframe assessments in light of GenAI's capabilities [14, 11, 3].

Adoption of GenAI is influenced by factors such as ease of use, perceived pedagogical value, and educators' attitudes toward technology. At the same time, issues of fairness, over-dependence, and alignment with curriculum goals present obstacles [7]. Prompt engineering has been suggested as a way to support deeper computational understanding [9].

While research on GenAI in higher education is growing, its use in secondary informatics remains underexplored. This stage is critical for developing computational thinking and programming skills.

This study addresses that gap by investigating how secondary informatics teachers envision incorporating large language models such as ChatGPT into their teaching. It explores the strategies they employ to support student learning and engagement, as well as the perceived benefits and challenges of using such tools.

Specifically, this paper addresses the following research questions:

1. In what ways do informatics teachers envision incorporating large language models such as ChatGPT into their teaching, and how do these strategies support student learning and engagement in Informatics?

2. What are teachers' perceived benefits and challenges of using large language models such as ChatGPT in the informatics classroom?

2 Methodology

2.1 The research context

This study was conducted in Malta, where secondary school students aged 11–16 follow a mandatory ICT subject designed to provide basic ICT entitlement. This includes skills such as word processing, presentations, spreadsheets, and basic programming. In addition to this mandatory subject, students aged 13–16 can opt to study an additional Informatics course. This course focusses on more advanced computer science topics, including programming in Python, databases, logic, and microcontrollers. The participants in this study were teachers from state, church, and independent schools in Malta, teaching the mandatory ICT subject or the optional Informatics course. They worked with students who had chosen Informatics as a specialised area of study. A total of 21 teachers (14 men and 7 women) with varying levels of teaching experience participated. Their teaching experience ranged from less than a year to more than 21 years, and they had different levels of familiarity with GenAI tools such as ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot (see Tables 1 and 2 for demographic details). Participants were recruited via an email sent by a gatekeeper to all Informatics teachers in Maltese secondary schools. Teachers were invited to express their interest by completing an online form. Within the form, participants were also asked to indicate their preference for the workshop modality (online or face-to-face). In addition, a Facebook post served as a reminder and consolidation method to maximise participation. This approach ensured broad outreach while minimising bias towards social media users. The study followed ethical guidelines and received informed consent from all participants regarding data collection, recording and analysis. The in-person

Table 1. Teaching experience of participating teachers

Years of Teaching Experience	Number of Teachers
21+ years	6
16–20 years	2
11–15 years	4
6–10 years	5
3–5 years	3
Less than a year	1

workshop was held at the University of Malta and lasted 4 hours, while the online workshop was conducted via Zoom. Both sessions followed a structured format:

Table 2. Familiarity with Large Language Models (LLMs) like ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot

Years of Teaching Experience	Yes – Used in teaching	Yes – Not used in teaching	No
21+ years	1	4	1
16–20 years	2		
11–15 years		4	
6–10 years	2	3	
3–5 years	2	1	
Less than a year	1		

1. **Introduction to LLMs:** The facilitator (author) provided a PowerPoint presentation and introduced participants to the use of LLMs, demonstrating their potential applications and addressing issues such as hallucination.
2. **Hands-on Practice:** Teachers engaged in guided exercises using ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot to gain practical experience.
3. **Group Discussions:** Participants formed subgroups to discuss the challenges and benefits of using LLMs in the classroom. Each subgroup documented their insights using Padlet, a digital collaborative tool.

2.2 Data Collection and Analysis

Data were collected through Padlet activity outputs, exit questionnaires, and workshop recordings (with participant consent). The online workshop session was recorded to ensure no data was missed. Subsequently, the recorded session was transcribed for further analysis. Participants' identities were anonymised to ensure confidentiality. The qualitative data underwent thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2006) methodology:

1. **Open Coding:** Raw data were systematically broken into smaller segments and assigned initial codes to identify emerging concepts.
2. **Axial Coding:** Relationships between categories were explored to deepen the analysis.
3. **Selective Coding:** Categories were integrated into a central theme for a comprehensive theoretical framework.

A single coder conducted the analysis. While only one coder was used, the process involved systematic and iterative coding to ensure consistency and thoroughness. This included revisiting the data multiple times and carefully documenting emerging themes and categories. Triangulation was employed by comparing data across multiple sources to enhance the validity and reliability of findings.

3 Analysis and Discussion

The thematic analysis yielded three main themes (see Figure 1). This section presents each theme with illustrative insights and links to relevant literature.

Fig. 1. Key themes emerging from thematic analysis

3.1 Theme 1: Enhancing Student Engagement and Personalised Learning

Student Engagement and Personalisation Teachers viewed LLMs like ChatGPT as effective for enhancing engagement and tailoring learning. One participant highlighted their use within a “3-Ps (play-practice-perform) model,” motivating students through active participation. Others noted that LLMs helped create dynamic, stimulating environments, particularly for high-achieving students—aligning with literature on GenAI’s role in supporting self-regulated learning and inclusivity [1, 21, 22, 10].

Autonomy and Differentiation LLMs were described as “study buddies 24/7,” offering on-demand support that helps students progress at their own pace. Participants noted their use in generating personalised explanations, simplifying complex content, and supporting differentiated learning. For example, one teacher said LLMs can “replace the F1 ‘Help!’ function key” in labs. These insights reinforce findings on GenAI’s potential to scaffold learning and reduce teacher workload while fostering autonomy [5, 30].

Inclusivity and Deeper Learning Teachers highlighted benefits for students with literacy difficulties and those facing language barriers. LLMs were praised for “tracing/debugging → deeper learning,” supporting comprehension and problem-solving in programming tasks. Such feedback underscores GenAI’s adaptability to diverse learner profiles and its role in cultivating deeper understanding [1, 21, 22, 10].

3.2 Theme 2: Teacher Support and Curriculum Enhancement

Efficiency and Professional Development Teachers appreciated LLMs for streamlining lesson and assessment design, freeing time for interactive teaching. One noted these tools “save time in resource preparation,” while cautioning

against over-reliance. Echoing hybrid intelligence principles, they emphasised co-creating resources with AI [6]. A call for “a structured programme to train all teachers” reflects the need for targeted professional development, as highlighted in GenAI integration literature [2].

Curriculum Relevance and Real-World Alignment LLMs were seen as useful for creating varied, realistic assessments and enabling student exploration of advanced topics. Teachers described them as aiding “student exploration of complex informatics concepts” and “preparing students for the real world” through practical applications. These insights align with research positioning GenAI as a tool for enhancing curriculum relevance and transferability [1, 20].

3.3 Theme 3: Assessment Challenges and Ethical Considerations

Assessment and Integrity Teachers expressed concern about evaluating understanding when students use LLMs. One commented, “formal assessment is going to be difficult to assess.” Others stressed the need to revise assessment practices to reflect GenAI use [14, 11, 3]. Calls to teach “critical thinking and evaluation” skills and integrate prompt engineering techniques were common [9, 17].

Misuse, Access, and Equity Risks of plagiarism and overreliance were frequently mentioned. As one participant warned, “students might see it as a way to completely outsource their work.” Concerns also included filtered access in schools, limited classroom time, and privacy risks tied to student data [16, 15, 17].

Teachers noted the need to “mentally shift how we teach,” acknowledging broader pedagogical implications. Concerns about dependency on technology and reduced human interaction were also voiced, with emphasis on maintaining balance between innovation and traditional relationships [2, 17, 3].

4 Discussion

This research aimed to address two key questions: how Informatics teachers envision incorporating LLMs like ChatGPT into their teaching practices to support student learning and engagement, and what the perceived benefits and challenges of using these models in the Informatics classroom are, according to teachers

4.1 Integration of LLMs into Teaching Practices

The first research question focused on how Informatics teachers envision integrating LLMs into their instructional approaches. The findings suggest that teachers view LLMs as powerful tools for enhancing student engagement and providing personalised support.

Teachers highlighted the capacity of LLMs to create more interactive and stimulating learning environments. The use of models like ChatGPT to introduce the 3-Ps (play-practice-perform) model was seen as an effective strategy to motivate students by leveraging their natural curiosity and enthusiasm. This approach aligns with the literature that emphasises the role of GenAI in fostering dynamic and engaging learning experiences [1, 21]. Moreover, LLMs were viewed as valuable resources for providing individualised support. Teachers noted that these models can cater to diverse learning needs and paces, ensuring that all students, regardless of their level, receive appropriate guidance. This ability to tailor educational content to meet individual needs was seen as crucial for maintaining high levels of student engagement and interest in Informatics. This finding supports previous research that highlights the role of GenAI in enhancing inclusivity and adaptability in education [1, 21]. Teachers also recognised the potential of LLMs to act as virtual learning assistants, providing continuous support and feedback to students. This capability was seen as particularly beneficial during independent study sessions, where students could use LLMs to generate self-learning exercises or seek help as needed. The idea of having a “study buddy 24/7” aligns with the notion of GenAI tools fostering self-regulated learning behaviours and providing on-demand support [22, 10].

4.2 Perceived Benefits and Challenges

The second research question explored the perceived benefits and challenges of using LLMs in the Informatics classroom. The findings revealed several key benefits, including enhanced student engagement, personalised support, facilitation of complex exploration, and preparation for real-world applications. Teachers noted that LLMs could significantly improve the quality and relevance of assessments by providing varied and realistic problem-solving scenarios. This was seen as crucial for helping students understand the practical applications of their learning, thereby preparing them for real-world challenges. The role of GenAI in curriculum development and enhancing the learning environment was also highlighted [1, 20]. However, the study also identified several challenges associated with the integration of LLMs. One major concern was the need to revise assessment methods to effectively incorporate LLMs. Teachers expressed difficulties in creating assessments that accurately measure students' understanding when using these advanced tools. This aligns with the literature that discusses the challenges of maintaining academic standards in the era of GenAI [11, 14]. Another significant challenge was the potential for inaccuracies and biases in LLM outputs. Teachers emphasised the importance of teaching students to critically assess the information provided by LLMs, highlighting the need for critical thinking and evaluation skills. This concern is supported by studies that underscore the potential for bias and inaccuracies in GenAI-generated content [17]. Teachers also raised concerns about the overreliance on technology, which could hinder the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The risk of students using LLMs to outsource their work entirely, rather than as a tool

for growth, was seen as a potential issue. This concern is echoed in the literature, which highlights the importance of balancing the use of GenAI tools with the development of essential cognitive skills [3, 11]. Additionally, practical challenges such as the filtering of LLMs in some schools, insufficient class time for experimentation, and privacy and security concerns related to student data were identified. These issues highlight the need for robust infrastructure and data protection measures to support the effective integration of LLMs in education [16, 15].

4.3 Limitations of this study

This research provides valuable insights into teachers' perceptions of integrating LLMs like ChatGPT into secondary school Informatics education; however, several limitations should be acknowledged. The sample consisted of 21 teachers from Maltese secondary schools. While this may appear small in absolute terms, it represents a substantial proportion of the local Informatics teaching population and is appropriate for qualitative research, which emphasises depth of insight over numerical representation. Nonetheless, generalisability to other educational contexts remains limited. Additionally, participant bias may have influenced the results, as those who volunteered were likely to have a pre-existing interest in or familiarity with generative AI tools. Future research should aim to include larger and more diverse samples, including individuals with varying levels of experience and enthusiasm, to provide a more balanced perspective.

Another limitation is the timing of data collection, as teachers' perceptions were captured immediately after a workshop. The workshop itself may have influenced their views on generative AI, potentially creating a positive bias due to the structured exposure and focused discussions. Longitudinal studies could help discern whether these initial impressions evolve over time with sustained use of the technology in teaching practice. The study focused on specific LLMs available at the time (e.g., ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot). With rapid advancements in AI, new tools may emerge, altering the educational technology landscape. Future research should consider these advancements and their implications.

5 Conclusions

Reflecting on the findings, it becomes clear that teachers see LLMs as powerful allies in educational contexts, but they also express understandable concerns regarding assessment. This dual perspective presents a unique opportunity to re-examine and revitalise the flipped classroom model, which has been idealised but underutilised in practice [4]. The integration of LLMs can enhance the flipped classroom approach by promoting a student-centred learning environment where students take the lead in their education, using LLMs to explore and engage with material independently. In a flipped classroom, students prepare for class by engaging with instructional content, such as videos or readings, outside of the

classroom. Class time is then dedicated to interactive, application-based activities facilitated by the teacher. LLMs can significantly augment this model by providing students with personalised, immediate feedback and support during their preparatory work, effectively functioning as “study buddies” that help them grasp complex concepts at their own pace [26]. Moreover, this approach encourages a shift in assessment methods towards “assessment as learning” [25]. Instead of traditional summative assessments, students continuously evaluate their understanding through interactive exercises and peer discussions, often guided by LLM-generated prompts and questions. This not only fosters deeper learning but also prepares students for real-world problem-solving by encouraging them to actively participate in their learning process [26].

5.1 Policy Recommendations Following the Teachers' Voices

To effectively integrate large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT into secondary school Informatics education, policymakers must take comprehensive and strategic actions. Structured training programs for educators are urgently needed, focusing on equipping teachers with the skills to effectively use LLMs in their teaching. These programs should cover technical aspects as well as best practices for fostering students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills to prevent overreliance on AI-generated content. Policymakers should ensure robust infrastructure and support systems are in place. These systems must provide equitable access to technologies across all schools and establish clear guidelines on data privacy and security, creating a stable and secure environment for using LLMs in classrooms. To mitigate academic dishonesty and ensure the reliability of AI-generated content, schools should develop and enforce comprehensive Acceptable Use Policies (AUPs). These policies should guide the ethical use of LLMs by students and teachers, emphasizing originality and critical evaluation of AI-generated content.

5.2 Further research

Building on this study's findings and limitations, several research avenues are recommended. Longitudinal studies tracking the long-term effects of integrating LLMs into secondary education would provide deeper insights into their impact on teaching, student engagement, and learning outcomes. Expanding research to diverse cultural and educational contexts can identify universal versus context-specific benefits and challenges. Comparative studies across different countries and educational systems would be particularly valuable. Investigating students' perceptions and experiences with LLMs can offer a more holistic view of their impact, exploring how different demographics (e.g., age, academic level, and individual learning preferences) interact with these technologies.

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